

TEACHING ENGLISH BASED ON A PERSON-ORIENTED APPROACH

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***Annotation:** English language teaching based on a person-oriented approach is one of the most effective methods. In this article, some directions of English language teaching will be discussed.*

***Keywords:** Education, Foreign Languages, Grammar, Lexicus, Attention, Training Material, Methodology.*

INTRODUCTION

A personality-oriented lesson, in contrast to the traditional one, primarily changes the type of interaction “teacher-learning”. From the command style, the teacher proceeds to cooperation, focusing on analysis not so much of results as the student’s procession. The positions of the student are changing - from diligent performance to active creativity, his thinking becomes different: reflexive, that is, aimed at the result. The nature of the relationship of relationships also changes. The main thing is that the teacher should not only give knowledge, but also create optical conditions for the development of the personality of students. A personality-oriented submission in learning is inconceivable without identifying the subjective experience of each learning, that is, his abilities and skills in educational activities. The main goal of learning with this approach is to create favorable conditions for the development of personality. However, the experience of each person is purely individual and has a variety of features¹.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

¹ G.Motteram. Innovations in learning technologies for English language teaching. GB: —British council band and designl, 2013, 200p.

In the preparation and conduct of a personality-oriented lesson, the teacher needs to know the characteristics of the subjective experience of the training, this will help him choose rational techniques, means, methods and forms of work individually for everyone.

The purpose of the didactic material, which is in such a lesson, is to work out the curriculum, teach students the necessary knowledge, skills, skills. Types of didactic material: training texts, cards-stake, didactic tests. Tasks are developed on topics, according to the level of complexity, on the purpose of use, according to the number of operations based on a multi-level differentiated and individual approach taking into account the leading type of student activity of the student (cognitive, communicative, creative). This approach is based on the possibility of evaluating the level of achievement in mastering knowledge, skills. Various types of didactic material do not replace, but complement each other.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The technology of personality-oriented learning involves the special design of the educational text, didactic and methodological material to its use, types of educational dialogue, forms of monitoring the student's sensitive development.

Pedagogy, focused on the individuals of the student, should reveal his subjective experience and provide him with the opportunity to choose the methods and forms of educational work and the nature of the answers. At the same time, not only the result is evaluated, but also the process of their achievements.

In this context, we developed a lesson - a role -playing game on the basis of one of the lessons of the vocabulary of oral and written language "Proficiency C2", the authors - Virginia Evans & Jenny Dooley². The lesson is designed for students of 2-4 courses of language universities. This lesson is non -standard, because the role -playing game is unprepared speech, which undoubtedly develops the speech aspect of communication and takes into account the personal experience of students. Students already know the text according to which the game is proposed, and are

² H.Emery, S.Rich. Teaching English to young learners. -USA: —Gasch Printing, LLC, Odenton, Maryland USAI, 2015, 42p.

also equipped with handouts in the form of cards with their roles and new words. Thus, their active independent activity is stimulated during the lesson, they use the experience of previous classes and learn something new. Lesson- a role-playing game is aimed at independent selection and use of the most acceptable and significant ways to work out educational material, since students know only roles with a description of the behavior model that they independently choose, as well as setting on what problem they need during the lesson decide.

Features of a personal approach are visible in the lesson in four aspects: in the organization of the lesson itself; In a different position of the teacher in relation to the student and to the educational process, to the role of the teacher in it; in a different position of the student himself as a subject of educational activity³; In a different nature of the mutual executions between the teacher and the student in the educational process. In accordance with this, we conducted a comparative analysis of the lesson with a personality-oriented approach compared to the usual English lesson. On the basis of this comparison, the comparison is clearly traced that the formation of the communicative competence of students in the lesson using a personality-oriented approach is better than in the usual lesson in the English language, since all the characteristics of the lesson that allow the teacher to realize the necessary technological indicators of the educational process, which The usual lesson in English is not fully implemented.

CONCLUSION

Thus, English lessons turn into such classes where each student not only assimilates certain knowledge, but also learns himself, learns to control himself, evaluate his real opportunities, predict ways to develop them. Thus, the student not only shows his personal qualities, but also forms himself as a person, while studying a foreign language.

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³ Tisdaliev S.S. Early from methods of teaching foreign languages. -Namangi: NamSU, 2014 y.

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